

$\{[\text{Mn}_2(\text{L-tartrate})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})].3\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ – A chiral MOF : Adsorption and guest dependent magnetism

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Abstract : A 3D nano-porous chiral metal-organic framework (CMOF), namely, $\{[\text{Mn}_2(\text{tartrate})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})].3\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ has been synthesized at room temperature by stirring method from mixture of $\text{MnCl}_2.6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with chiral L(+)-tartrate ligand. X-Ray single crystal structure analysis indicates that complex 1 crystallizes in chiral $P2_1$ space group. Complex 1 forms only left handed helical coordination chains along crystallographic *c*-axis and becomes homochiral. During formation of 3D coordination framework, 1D porous channel is created along crystallographic *c*-axis where guest water molecules get stability through hydrogen bonding interactions. The framework remains crystalline after loss of guest water molecules and adsorption study was done with this evacuated framework. The evacuated framework shows nano-porosity and adsorbs 22 ml g⁻¹ N₂ at 77 K with type III adsorption isotherm. Guest dependent magnetic study has been carried out. Both complex 1 and the evacuated complex exhibit antiferromagnetic behavior.

Keywords : 3D metal-organic framework, homochirality, adsorption study, guest dependent magnetic behavior.

Introduction

For the past few decades, interest on metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) has increased enormously not only owing to their structural diversities but also due to their potential functionalities¹⁻⁴. Nowadays, it is highly desirable to combine as many as possible properties into a single MOF, namely, multifunctional MOF, for their burgeoning application in diverse areas. Recently, increasing efforts are being put forth to design multifunctional MOFs with a set of excellent properties such as magnetism with porosity, magnetism with optical properties, magnetism with photo-reactivity, magnetism with conductivity etc.⁵⁻⁹. To achieve such synergism, where two different functionalities are combined, researchers are exploring new routes to design and synthesize multifunctional materials. Chiral metal-organic frameworks (CMOFs) can display multifunctionality. Because of their intrinsic chirality, CMOFs exhibit NLO activity, enantioselective catalysis, separation etc.¹⁰⁻¹⁵. Now, these properties of CMOFs can also be combined with other material properties like porosity, magnetism etc.¹⁶⁻²⁰.

Thus, the research on CMOFs has attracted much attention beyond the fundamental search of chirality and molecular recognition and consequently the design and synthesis of chiral MOFs have become a great challenge to crystal engineers.

According to Moulton and Zaworotko²¹, in general, three strategies can be adopted to synthesize CMOFs : (i) the utilization of a chiral connector; (ii) the exploitation of both chiral and achiral ligands to break the symmetry and (iii) the use of molecules where spontaneous chiral resolution occurs²²⁻²⁷. Recently, we have developed two CMOFs namely, $\{[\text{Cu}_2(1,10\text{-phen})_2(\text{tartrate})\text{H}_2\text{O}].8\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ and $\{[\text{Cu}(1,10\text{-phen})(\text{H}_2\text{-tartrate})\text{H}_2\text{O}].6\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$, using chiral ligand L(+)-tartrate utilizing the 1st strategy described above and established that L(+)-tartrate is a robust ligand for the formation of homochiral metal-organic frameworks with helicity¹⁴.

Generally, dicarboxylate ligands are used to bridge the metal centers and they provide magnetic exchange pathway among the metal centers which introduces ferromagnetic, ferrimagnetic, antiferromagnetic interactions and

also spin canting in the system²⁸⁻³². Moreover, porosity can also be achieved in such magnetic coordination polymers^{9,20,33}. Now, our aim is to pursue magneto-porous multifunctional CMOFs. Tartrate, a dicarboxylate ligand, shows variable coordination ability and can coordinate with more than one metal centers. As a result, coordination polymers of various dimensions (1D or 2D or 3D) can be formed. So, chiral L(+)-tartrate ligand can be used to synthesize multifunctional coordination polymer with intrinsic chirality.

Very recently, Tabatabaee *et al.*³⁴ have reported structure and thermal property of a Mn-tartrate complex, $\{[\text{Mn}_2(\text{L-tartrate})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ (complex 1) synthesized by solvothermal method. But, they are silent about the chirality of the complex and have not explored the material properties. On the other hand according to Saha *et al.* metal organic complexes of L(+)-tartrate should exhibit chirality with helicity¹⁴. In this context, it will be interesting to (i) examine the possibility of chirality in complex 1 through proper structural analysis; (ii) investigate whether porosity can be generated in framework upon evacuation of guest water molecules and (iii) study the guest depended magnetic property of the complex. In this background, we report synthesis, characterizations and magnetic property of the chiral 3D framework, $\{[\text{Mn}_2(\text{L-tartrate})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$ prepared by stirring method at room temperature. In this paper, we show that complex 1 displays chirality and exhibits porosity upon evacuation of guest water molecules. Guest dependent magnetic behavior of the framework has also been reported.

Experimental

Materials and physical methods : Mn^{II} chloride, hexahydrate and L(+)-disodiumtartrate were purchased from Merck chemical company. And all other chemicals used were AR grade. Elemental analysis (C, H, N) was carried out using a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. The thermal analysis was carried out using a Mettler Toledo TGA-DTA 85 thermal analyzer under a flow of dinitrogen (30 ml min^{-1}). The sample was heated at a rate of $10 \text{ }^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ with inert alumina as a reference. IR spectroscopy was measured on Nicolet Impact 410 spectrometer between 400 and 4000 cm^{-1} , using the KBr pellet method. The solid-state (KBr pellets) circular dichroism (CD) spectra were recorded on a JASCO J-810 spectropolarimeter. Powder XRD pattern of the compounds

were recorded by using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation (Bruker D8; 40 kV, 40 mA). Variable temperature (3–300 K) magnetization data were recorded using a SQUID magnetometer (MPMS Quantum design Excel 7). The experimental susceptibility data were corrected for underlying diamagnetism by use of tabulated Pascal's constants.

Gas adsorption study : Gas sorption isotherms for pressures in the range of 0–1 bar were measured using an Autosorb iQ (Quantachrome Inc., USA) gas sorption system. A sample of ca. 50 mg of as-synthesized material was introduced into a preweighed analysis tube (6 mm diameter, 6 cm^3 bulb), capped with a gas-tight transeal to prevent leakage of air and moisture during transfer and weighing. The samples were evacuated under dynamic vacuum (10^{-3} torr) at desired temperature, until a constant weight was achieved. The analysis tube was then weighed again to determine the mass of the evacuated sample. For all isotherms, warm and cold free space correction measurements were performed using ultrahigh pure He gas (99.999% purity). N_2 isotherm at 77 K was measured in a liquid nitrogen bath using ultrahigh pure (99.999% purity) gas source.

Synthesis of complex 1 $\{[\text{Mn}_2(\text{L-tartrate})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}\}_n$: Mn^{II} chloride, hexahydrate (0.1964 g, 1 mmol) dissolved in 10 ml distilled water was mixed with 5 ml of an aqueous solution of disodium tartrate (0.2302 g, 1 mmol). The whole mixture was stirred for 30 min. Light pink solution was filtered and filtrate was kept in dessicator. After 96 h cube shaped light pink crystals suitable for X-ray structural study were obtained, these were separated and dried. Yield 70% (Found : C, 20.15; H, 3.30. Calcd. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_{16}\text{Mn}_2$: C, 20.10; H, 3.37%); IR (KBr pellet, cm^{-1}) : 3427(s), 1610(s), 1519(w), 1446(s), 1368(s), 1218(w), 1132(w), 1079(w), 1055(w), 805(w); UV-Vis : λ_{max} 262, 371, 507 nm.

Crystallographic data collection and refinement : Suitable single crystal of the complex was mounted on a Bruker SMART diffractometer equipped with a graphite monochromator and $\text{MoK}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) radiation. The structure was solved using Patterson method by using the SHELXS 97. Subsequent difference Fourier synthesis and least-square refinement revealed the positions of the remaining non hydrogen atoms. Non-hydrogen atoms were refined with independent anisotropic displacement param-

eters. Hydrogen atoms were placed in idealized positions and their displacement parameters were fixed to be 1.2 times larger than those of the attached non-hydrogen atom. Successful convergence was indicated by the maximum shift/error of 0.001 for the last cycle of the least squares refinement. All calculations were carried out using SHELXS 97³⁵, SHELXL 97³⁶, PLATON 99³⁷, ORTEP-32³⁸ and WinGX system Ver-1.64³⁹. Data collection and structure refinement parameters and crystallographic data for complex **1** are given in Table S1. Some selected bond lengths, bond angles and noncovalent interaction parameters are summarized in Tables S2-S3.

Table S1. Crystallographic data collection and refinement parameters of complex **1**

Formula	C ₈ H ₁₀ Mn ₂ O ₁₃ ·3(H ₂ O)
Formula weight	478.09
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ (No. 4)
<i>a</i> (Å)	7.604(2)
<i>b</i> (Å)	11.100(4)
<i>c</i> (Å)	8.984(3)
α (°)	90
β (°)	99.723(6)
γ (°)	90
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	747.4(4)
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>D</i> (calcd.) (g/cm ³)	2.124
μ(MoK _α) (mm)	1.783
<i>F</i> (000)	484
Crystal size (mm)	0.20 × 0.22 × 0.28
Temperature (K)	293
Radiation (Angstrom)	MoK _α 0.71073
Theta Min-Max (Deg)	2.3, 28.4
Tot.	8903
Uniq. data	3581
R(int)	0.051
Observed data [<i>I</i> > 2.0 σ(<i>I</i>)]	2761
Nref	3581
Npar	231
R	0.0654
wR2	0.1656
S	1.00
Max. and Av. shift/error	0.00, 0.00
Flack <i>x</i>	0.03(8)
Min. and Max. Resd. Dens. (e/Å ³)	-0.72, 1.37

Table S2. Some selected bond lengths (Å) and bond angles (°) of complex **1**

Mn1-O1	2.192(10)	Mn1-O2	2.178(10)
Mn1-O9	2.100(10)	Mn1-O4W	2.130(11)
Mn1-O8_f	2.256(12)	Mn1-O11_f	2.141(10)
Mn2-O7	2.308(10)	Mn2-O10	2.137(12)
Mn2-O3_b	2.144(9)	Mn2-O12_d	2.150(11)
Mn2-O5_e	2.114(10)	Mn2-O6_e	2.275(10)
O1-Mn1-O2	73.5(4)	O1-Mn1-O4W	89.2(4)
O1-Mn1-O9	161.2(4)	O1-Mn1-O8_f	90.3(4)
O1-Mn1-O11_f	91.9(4)	O2-Mn1-O4W	95.2(4)
O2-Mn1-O9	88.6(4)	O2-Mn1-O8_f	96.1(4)
O2-Mn1-O11_f	161.8(4)	O4W-Mn1-O9	86.9(4)
O4W-Mn1-O8_f	168.1(4)	O4W-Mn1-O11_f	95.3(4)
O8_f-Mn1-O9	97.4(4)	O9-Mn1-O11_f	106.8(4)
O8_f-Mn1-O11_f	72.7(4)	O7-Mn2-O10	71.8(4)
O3_b-Mn2-O7	159.3(4)	O7-Mn2-O12_d	92.6(4)
O5_e-Mn2-O7	89.7(4)	O6_e-Mn2-O7	84.3(3)
O3_b-Mn2-O10	88.2(4)	O10-Mn2-O12_d	101.3(5)
O5_e-Mn2-O10	159.0(5)	O6_e-Mn2-O10	94.4(4)
O3_b-Mn2-O12_d	96.7(4)	O3_b-Mn2-O5_e	108.9(4)
O3_b-Mn2-O6_e	92.1(3)	O5_e-Mn2-O12_d	88.9(4)
O6_e-Mn2-O12_d	162.2(4)	O5_e-Mn2-O6_e	73.6(4)

*Symmetry : b = x, y, 1+z; d = 1-x, 112+y, 2-z; e = 2-x, -1/2+y, 2-z; f = 2-x, 1/2+y, 2-z.

Results and discussion

Structural description of complex 1 : Complex **1** crystallizes in chiral *P*2₁ space group. The single crystal X-ray diffraction analysis reveals that the complex **1** is a 3D coordination framework. Each asymmetric unit contains two Mn²⁺ ions, two tartrate²⁻ ligands, one coordinated and three guest water molecules. The ORTEP diagram of the asymmetric unit without guest water molecules is shown in the Fig. 1. Some selected bond lengths and bond angles are given in the Table S2. Both Mn atoms show distorted octahedral geometry but their coordination environments are different. The asymmetric unit contains two tartrate anions and their bridging patterns are also different. Among four carboxylate groups of two tartrates, three carboxylate groups show *syn-anti* bridging pattern with metal centers.

Tartrates bridges the metal nodes and thus only single stranded left handed helical coordination chains are formed along crystallographic *c*-axis with pitch of 8.894 Å, (Fig. 2). Due to presence of only left handed helical chains,

Table S3. Hydrogen bond dimensions of complex 1

D-H...A	D...H/(Å)	H...A/(Å)	D...A/(Å)	<D-H...A/(°)	Symmetry
O6-H1O6...O3W	0.9100	2.0500	2.875(16)	149.00	-1+x, y, z
O7-H1O7...O11	0.9000	1.8400	2.698(14)	158.00	1-x, 1/2+y, 2-z
O8-H1O8...O1W	0.8400	1.8100	2.648(19)	175.00	
O1-H1O1...O2W	0.9400	1.8300	2.565(18)	133.00	
O1W-H1W1...O9	0.9900	2.5100	3.23(2)	129.00	
O1W-H1W1...O11	0.9900	2.5800	3.42(2)	143.00	2-x, 1/2+y, 2-z
O1W-H2W1...O2W	0.8500	1.9600	2.57(2)	128.00	3-x, -1/2+y, 2-z
O1W-H2W1...O3W	0.8500	2.1900	2.66(3)	115.00	3-x, -1/2+y, 2-z
O2W-H1W2...O2	0.8400	2.2200	2.860(19)	133.00	1+x, y, z
O2W-H2W2...O4	1.1000	2.4500	3.50(2)	160.00	
O3W-H1W3...O4	0.8500	2.5900	3.433(18)	172.00	
O3W-H1W3...O5	0.8500	2.1400	2.723(16)	125.00	
O4W-H2W4...O12	0.8500	2.4800	3.316(15)	168.00	1+x, y, z
O4W-H2W4...O3	0.8500	2.4100	2.792(14)	108.00	2-x, -1/2+y, 1-z
C2-H2...O4	0.9800	2.4800	2.815(18)	100.00	
C3-H3...O9	0.9800	2.4800	3.393(17)	155.00	2-x, 1/2+y, 1-z
C6-H6...O4	0.9800	2.4200	3.299(18)	149.00	2-x, -1/2+y, 1-z

the framework becomes homochiral. These coordination helices are bridged by tartrate ligands and thus 3D coordination framework is formed (Fig. 3). During formation of 3D framework, complex 1 forms 1D porous channels where three guest water molecules get stability (Fig. 4). And also, the coordinated water molecule is hanging towards the channel. The guest water molecules are connected to the framework through hydrogen bonding interactions.

CD spectral analysis : Solid state CD spectral analysis was done with bulk crystals in the powder form within the wavelength range of 200–400 nm (Fig. 5). The result indicates that complex 1 has negative cotton effect at 228 nm and so complex 1 is homochiral in nature. The result also indicates that racemization of the ligand does not occur during synthesis and the stereochemical information transfers from the ligand to the framework.

Thermal and PXRD analysis : Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out to examine the thermal stability of complex 1. The result shows that complex 1 is stable in air at ambient temperature, which makes it potential candidate for practical applications. The sample was heated up under flow of N₂ with a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ within the temperature range of 30–600 °C, as shown in Fig. S1. Thermal analysis indicates that the

guest and coordinated water molecules are lost (theo = 15.12% and exp = 12.95%) within the temperature range of 80–140 °C. The desolvated complex starts decomposition after 200 °C.

The phase purity of the as synthesized complex was measured by PXRD (Fig. 7) analysis. The as-synthesized complex was heated at 150 °C for 4 h to remove all water molecules and then PXRD analysis was done again. The PXRD pattern reveals that after loss of all water molecules the framework remains crystalline. But, PXRD pattern of the evacuated complex is drastically different compared to that of the complex 1 (Fig. 6). Some new peaks have been found and peak shifting has also been noticed. This indicates that upon removal of water molecules structural transformation occurs within the framework and rearranges itself in a new framework. Further, due to removal of the coordinated water molecule, the coordination environment of Mn^{II} ion will be distorted and may create unsaturated metal centers (UMCs).

In order to investigate the reabsorption capability of the evacuated complex, we have kept it in open air for 48 h and PXRD data was taken again. But, no further change in the PXRD pattern was observed.

Adsorption study : As-synthesized material contains three guest and one coordinated water molecules per unit

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram of complex **1** (30% atomic probability) (*= $2-x, 0.5+y, 2-z$) : (a) coordination environment of Mn1 and (b) coordinaton environment of Mn2.

cell. PLATON indicates that after removal of all four water molecules, the framework contains 79 \AA^3 (10.6%) void space per unit cell. Thermal analysis indicates that within $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ all water molecules are lost. Now to determine the porosity of the framework, gas adsorption experiment was done with evacuated sample.

To measure the porosity of the framework, we have carried out N_2 adsorption study at 77 K (Fig. 7). The N_2

adsorption isotherm study revealed type III isotherm. The isotherm shows that up to relative pressure $P/P_0 = 0.8$, the framework adsorbs only 5.4 ml/g N_2 gas but after this adsorption amount increases sharply to 22 ml/g at $P/P_0 = 0.99$. The gas molecules enter within the pores and monolayer formation takes place. Desorption curve does not match with the adsorption curve and a small hysteresis has been found in this case. It may be due to

Fig. 2. Helical coordination chain formation along crystallographic *c*-axis (color scheme : C = cyan, O = red, Mn = green).

Fig. 3. 3D porous framework, void space is denoted by yellow color (color scheme : C = cyan, O = red, Mn = violet).

Fig. 4. Water molecules get stability within the framework (color scheme : C = cyan, O = red, Mn = violet, H = white).

Fig. 5. CD spectra of complex 1.

Fig. 6. PXRD pattern of complex 1.

Fig. S1. Thermal plot of complex 1.

Fig. 7. Adsorption N₂ isotherm of complex 1.

interaction between the unsaturated metal centers (UMCs) with the adsorbed gas molecules^{40,41}. The adsorption study reveals that the evacuated sample behaves like a nanoporous material⁴².

Guest dependent magnetic study : Guest dependent magnetic behavior of porous frameworks has attracted much attention from last decade⁴³⁻⁴⁵. Here, we have studied the variable temperature magnetic behavior of the as-synthesized complex and of the evacuated complex.

Variable temperature magnetic behavior of complex 1 : Variable temperature magnetic studies have been performed on powdered samples of complex 1 in the temperature range 3–300 K. The χ_m vs T and $\chi_m T$ vs T plots of complex 1 are shown in Fig. 8. The value of χ_m at 300 K is 0.026 cm³ mol⁻¹, upon cooling χ_m value increases very slowly to 0.15 cm³ mol⁻¹ at 51 K and afterward increases smoothly to reach a value of 1.14 cm³ mol⁻¹ at 3 K. In order to determine the nature of magnetic interaction, the susceptibility data were fitted to the Curie-Weiss

Fig. 8. χ_m vs T and $\chi_m T$ vs T plot of complex 1.

law. Curie and Weiss constants are $8.17 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ and $\theta = -4.70 \text{ K}$, respectively (Fig. 2). The negative value of the Weiss constant indicates strong antiferromagnetic interaction between Mn^{II} ions. The value of $\chi_m T$ at 300 K is $8.10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$, which is slightly smaller than the calculated spin only value for two Mn^{II} ($S = 5/2$) ions ($4.375 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ for one Mn^{II} ion), indicates that antiferromagnetic interaction is present within the Mn^{II} ions of the complex. Upon cooling, $\chi_m T$ first decreases very slowly to reach a value of $7.67 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ at 51 K and then it decreases drastically to a minimum of $3.42 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ at 3 K, suggesting an appreciable antiferromagnetic exchange interaction between Mn centers.

Variable temperature magnetic behavior of the evacuated complex : Variable temperature magnetic behavior of the evacuated complex has been studied in the temperature range 3–300 K. The χ_m vs T and $\chi_m T$ vs T plots of complex 1 are shown in Fig. 9. The value of χ_m at 300 K is $0.025 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, upon cooling χ_m value increases very slowly to $0.14 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 51 K and afterward

Fig. 9. χ_m vs T and $\chi_m T$ vs T plot of the evacuated complex.

increases smoothly to reach a value of $0.85 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 3 K. Curie and Weiss constants are $7.80 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ and $\theta = -5.66 \text{ K}$, respectively (Fig. S3). The negative value of the Weiss constant indicates strong antiferromagnetic interaction between Mn^{II} ions. The value of $\chi_m T$ at 300 K is $7.66 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$, upon cooling $\chi_m T$ first decreases very slowly to reach a value of $7.09 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ at 51 K and then it decreases drastically to a minimum of $2.56 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ K}$ at 3 K. So, antiferromag-

Fig. S2. χ_m^{-1} vs T plot of complex 1.

Fig. S3. χ_m^{-1} vs T plot of the evacuated complex.

netic exchange interaction is present between Mn centers within the evacuated complex.

Thus, upon removal of guest and coordinated water molecules, the χ_m and Weiss constant decreases, hence the antiferromagnetic interaction increases within the system.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we have successfully established the material properties associated with the chiral 3D metal organic framework synthesized by using enantiomerically pure chiral L(+)-tartrate ligand at room temperature. This complex is crystallized in chiral $P2_1$ space group and forms helical coordination chain along crystallographic c -axis of left handed helicity. The homochirality of the framework is checked by CD spectral analysis which cor-

roborates the results of structural analysis. The nano-porous complex, after removal of water molecules, shows N_2 adsorption with small hysteresis. Guest dependent magnetic behavior indicates upon removal of water molecules antiferromagnetic interaction has been enhanced.

Finally, this chiral framework can be used a multi-functional material. And, further studies on chiral framework using tartrate ligand may enable us to couple ferromagnetism and porosity with chirality.

Supplementary materials : CCDC no. of complex 1 is 806999. This data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>. or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44)-1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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